

Advanced Concept of Cogeneration System for Efficient Waste Heat Recovery in Thermal Power Plants

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Abstract: The Thermal power plants (TTP) are traditionally associated or mainly known for the substantial energy losses in the form of heat that is primarily in the form of unused or waste heat which is released into the environment. In this not only reduces the overall efficiency of power generation but also effect in the degradation of environment. It drawn attention towards the advanced method or system of cogeneration that will efficiently be able to recover, reduce and utilize the waste heat of power stations (TTPs). The system that is proposed for minimizing the waste heat integrates the technologies such as thermoelectric generators which is used to convert the low-grade waste heat into usable electrical or thermal energy, combined heat and power (CHP) configurations and Organic Rankine Cycles (ORC). By optimized thermodynamic cycles and doing process control based on real-time process control system the waste heat can be reduced and chances of improvements of the entire power plant efficiency, energy generation, energy losses, power saving and carbon footprints reduced which will be more economical which leads towards the next level or next generation of providing power facilities. Simulation, guidance and concept of reducing waste heat are required towards the more sustainable along with high energy-efficient power generation infrastructures.

Keywords: Thermal Power Plant, Environment, Technologies, Carbon footprints, Power saving, Waste Heat losses, Energy-efficient

Introduction: The main source of electricity generation in the world level is still depends upon Thermal Power Plant (TPP). As we know that in generating electricity from TPP based on traditional process there is a huge loss of waste heat. This not only count in the burning of more fuel and enlarging wastage of energy but also impact on polluting the environment in a large scale. To face or overcome this challenge the concept of cogeneration system is introduced. The other name of cogeneration system is combined heat and power (CHP) which have come into view as an emerging technique that is highly effective towards the solution to reduce waste heat.

Cogeneration not only increases the production of electricity but also uses the thermal heat that is from the same source of fuel thus by reducing the level of discharge heat and increases the production of electricity from 30-40% to 60-90% from the traditional setup.

This setup not only increases productivity by reducing in burning of fuel but also making the environment less polluted by reducing the carbon emission. By introducing CHP system we can utilize waste heat in commercially and domestically application.

The TPP can retrofit CHP by installing heat recovery system generators (HRSGs) and proper steam distribution systems or networks which can be able to utilize the low- pressure steam or hot water. The setup of this TTP must be near to the industrial zone so that loss in transportations can be minimized.

Cogeneration system is based on the generation of electricity and utility of heat simultaneously from a single source of energy that is from coal, biogas, biomass, natural gas and waste heat. The concept of cogeneration introduced to utilizes the waste heat which helps in improving the overall efficiency to TPP.

Types of CHP:

Figure 1: Types of combined heat and power

As the term cogeneration indicates the system that involves in the generation of electricity as well as steam (heat) at the same time for getting a better return on investment (ROI) based on investment for setting up TPP.

$$\text{Cogeneration efficiency: } \eta_{\text{co}} = \frac{E + \Delta H_s}{Q_A}$$

Where E= Generation of Electric Energy from Power Plant

ΔH_s = Heat energy dissipated from the process steam

Enthalpy of steam entering the process – enthalpy of process condensate

Q_A = Heat added in to the plant by burning of the fuel

For the generating of electricity and steam separately, the heat added in the plant in term of per unit of total energy is

$$\frac{e}{\eta_e} + \frac{(1+e)}{\eta_h}$$

Where, e = electrical fraction of total energy output = $[E/(E + \Delta H_s)]$

η_e = electric plant efficiency

η_h = steam, (or heat) generator efficiency

By combining the two equation of separate generation

$$\eta_c = \frac{1}{(e/\eta_e) + [(1-e)\eta_h]}$$

If $\eta_{co} > \eta_c$; then the cogeneration will provide a better ROI

Figure 2: Cogeneration Power Plant System

Waste Energy Management (WEM): The CHP provides the mechanism of recover the waste heat by using it effectively. By this the overall efficiency of Power Plant increases. The WEM system involves-

- Heat Recovery Units (HRUs): In this we use devices such as heat exchangers which are used to capture the exhaust heat that comes from turbine and can be reuse for hot water, hot steam or process heating
- Thermal Storage: It is the method by which excess heat is stores during low consumption or low demand and utilize the same during peak hours of demands thus it balance the supply load or energy load
- Absorption Chillers: It is use to convert the waste heat or waste steam into cooling energy by using the concept of district cooling commonly known as industrial refrigeration (This entire process is known as Trigenation).

Technical Possibility for Cogeneration: The CHP provides us a wide range of implementing the technologies in the traditional power plant to increase its efficiency that may be up to 85 percentages or more in some conditions along with various applications which benefits the economic activities.

Figure 3: Cogeneration (Cogen) Advantages

Suppose here is an example of CHP in which an industry needs 36 units of electrical energy and it also requires 32 units of heat energy. If the plant separates the route of heat and energy the primary source of energy input in the plant will be 60 units $(36/0.35)$. If the plant uses different boiler to get steam then the fuel requires for obtaining steam of 40 units that is $(40/0.7)$. On the other hand in a cogeneration plant the input fuel is only 54 units $[(36+32)/0.85]$ to obtain both heat and electricity. Heat loss is only 15 units on the other hand it is 46 units.

Heat to Power Ratio: It is the almost important and vital technical factor which guide and influence the entire setup of the cogeneration system. It reflects the efficiency of CHP. It indicates the energy and heat requirement that is fulfilled by the burning of fuel.

Cogen Plant System	Heat - to - Power Ratio (kWth/kWe)	Power Output (percent of fuel input)	Percentage of Overall Efficiency
Reciprocating engine	2.5	53	85
Combined cycle (Gas – Steam Turbine)	1.7	40	83
Gas turbine	2.0	35	85
Extraction-condensing steam turbine	2.0 – 10	40	80
Back-pressure steam turbine	14.3	28	92

Figure 1: Heat to Power Ratio for different types of Turbine

Figure 4: Heat to Power Ratio for different types of Turbine

Heat to Power Ratio for Energy Intensive Industries:

Types of Industries	Minimum	Maximum	Average
Breweries	1.1	4.5	3.1
Pharmaceuticals	1.5	2.5	2.0
Fertilizer	0.8	3.0	2.0
Food	0.8	2.5	1.2
Paper	1.5	2.5	1.9

Table2: Heat to Power Ratio for Energy Intensive Industries

Figure 5: Heat to Power Ratio for Energy Intensive Industries

Quality of Thermal Energy According to Need: The quality reflects or shows the types of cogen plant. It also indicates the required thermal energy that is in terms of pressure and temperature. The thermal energy needed for a sugar mill is at about 120°C to meet this we need CHP of topping cycle. On the other hand if we consider a cement plant then the thermal energy needed is at about 1450°C which we get from bottoming cycle CHP. In both case we can generate the electricity.

Factors Influencing Cogen: There are certain factors those effects the cogen system is based on following:

- The minimum and maximum requirement of the base electric demand should be maintained or matched
- The steam produced should be utmost utilized in the form of waste heat
- Proper maintenance should be done to increase the lifespan of plant
- Overall efficiency should be maintain
- Wastage of fuel should be minimum
- Plant cost should not be to high
- All things must be maintain within the stimulated time

Combustion ranges:**A. Gaseous Fuels**

Fuel	Stoichiometric Air/fuel Ratio (m³ air / m³ fuel)	Combustion of Heat (KJ/ft³)
Hydrogen (H ₂)	2.38	328
Carbon Monoxide (CO)	2.28	322
Methane (CH ₄)	9.53	1013
Propane (C ₃ H ₈)	23.82	2590
Natural Gas	9.4-11.0	950-1150
Coke Oven Gas	3.5-5.5	400-600

Table3: Combustion of Heat in Gaseous Fuel

B. Liquid Fuels

Fuel	Stoichiometric Air/fuel Ratio (m³ air / m³ fuel)	Combustion of Heat (KJ/ft³)
Carbon (C)	150	14.093
Sulphur (S)	56	3.983
Diesel	180-195	18500-19800
Oil	170-185	17500-19000

Table4: Combustion of Heat in Liquid Fuel

Cogeneration in Industries: The concept or idea of cogeneration system was introduced firstly in late 1880 in Europe and in early 20th century in USA. Later on many countries adopted this CHP system. As the demand of continuous electric supply and steam is increased in process industries mainly concerned with chemical, sugar mills, pharmaceuticals, dairy and food processing plants, hospitals, paper industries, breweries plants. These industries need uninterrupted energy supply in the form of heat and electricity to sustain the chemical process. To balance the ratio of heat and power supply these all above types of industries needs

cogeneration system as they can thus able to achieve their needs and optimizes the fuel to its maximum uses in term of thermal energy to generate electricity and steam and on the other hand to get maximum economic benefits.

Power Quality: In CHP the term power quality refers or termed as how well the plant generates the electricity by matching and maintaining the standard criteria that are required for the reliable, continuous, stable, uninterrupted and smooth operation of all electrical equipment or devices in terms of frequency, voltage, current, harmonics and others properties. Poor and bad power quality will tends towards the damage, malfunctioning and breakdown of the equipment installed, disturbances in grid and huge loss in energy.

Safety Features: It is the most crucial, vital feature in CHP system as it is a combination system where electricity, heat is generated simultaneously. To handle fuel in this system is also a tough task. Some important safety key features needed for this system must includes

- Fire Safety & Fire Alarm Systems
- Heat detector along with smoke sensors
- Proper Ventilation
- Automatic fuel injectors along with shut off valve in fuel line
- Gas Leakage Detectors
- Various Protection system for electrical equipment
- Proper temperature and Pressure handling equipment
- Interlocking
- Monitoring and controlling system
- Lockout-tagout (LOTO) procedures
- Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

Scope: The CHP has a wide scope as it is promising in generating electricity and steam simultaneously by using same fuel by decentralized the power solution. The combination of renewable energy system with cogen system will helps to balance the stability, sustainability and efficiency of power and heat. It plays a vital role in micro, smart and local grids by flexible generation of electricity. It will pollute less environments. It is resilient energy system.

Conclusion: The CHP has a high overall efficiency of energy that is 80-90% and conventional one has up to 45%. It reduces the combustion of fuel so it is cost and energy saving plant. It also reduces carbon emission. It provides stability and reliable power and steam generation. It is suitable for decentralization. Cogeneration Plant is capable to reduce or minimize the energy waste and gives maximum efficiency. The CHP has the ability to reduce lower greenhouse gas emission and less pollutes the surroundings. With the same fuel this plant is capable to generate electricity and utilize the thermal energy up to maximum strength. Cogen plant is economical

and cost saving plant. It is a modern concept of generating energy with high efficiency with a aim to minimize carbon footprints. The focus of this present study is based on the carrying out a concrete methodology to enhance the performances and efficiency of CHP Plant by making it robust and simple.

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